

REFLECTIVE PRACTICE: A KEY TO LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The study is an attempt to identify and suggest solutions to the problems of barriers in the process of language acquisition. The paper is based on an experimental study which highlights the need for incorporating various techniques used in reflective practices in different disciplines as well. The instructional design Reflective Language Acquisition Model (RLAM) provides ample exposure to the linguistic development of the students who learn English language. The phases of the instructional design is made up of theories of reflective practices and the linguistic principles of learning a language.

Key words: *Reflective practices, Task completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language control, etc.*

Introduction

Reflection is a vital component in language acquisition. It is an aid in learning as well as in the process of teaching. Without reflection or conscious awareness (Laskaris, 2016) of language elements, an individual cannot utilize the skills and sub skills of a language newly learnt. Reflective practices have become instrumental in improving one's practices in different professions and in new learning. In order to revamp language education, reflective practices are highly useful in developing language competencies.

Theories related to reflection emphasises that Reflective learning allows the learners to step back from their learning experience. Reflective teaching helps the teachers to equip themselves to become a professional in career. The syntax of the instructional design RLAM is framed on the linguistic principles of learning a language which has a deep influence on the entire syntax. The method adopted for the study is pretest posttest single group design. There are a lot of benefits (Davies, 2012) and advantages in applying reflective practices.

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- Increased learning from an experience or situation
- Promotion of deep learning
- Identification of areas for improvement about personal and professional strengths
- Identification of educational needs
- Acquisition of new knowledge and skills
- Further understanding of own beliefs, attitudes and values
- Encouragement of self-motivation and self-directed learning
- Act as a source of feedback
- Possible improvements in confidence

Reflective Practices in various disciplines

Generally reflective practices are being used for improving professional expertise. Now it has been used in various disciplines such as engineering, drama, art, teacher education, social work, nursing etc... Reflective strategies can improve rational thinking and metacognition. For examples, in engineering it has been widely applied in designing and redesigning the structure and devices. In social work, it is considered that reflective practice can help in developing professionalism, knowledge and critical reflection and analysis (Knott & Scragg, 2016).

Main theories incorporated in RLAM

Borton (1970)

Terry Borton's reflective model comprised of three questions which ask the practitioner – What, So what, and Now what? By analysis, the description of the situation leads to the scrutiny of the situation and construction of knowledge takes place. Eventually, the practitioners will be able to

identify the ways they can improve (Skinner & Mitchell, 2016).

Donald Schon(1983)

Theory of Schon explicitly mentions two types of reflective practices namely reflection in action and reflection on action. The former denotes the ongoing analysis of the activity in which the learner is involved. The later tells about the process of thinking back on what the learner has done in order to find out how ones knowing in action may have contributed to a particular result.

Graham Gibbs(1988)-Reflective cycle

The reflective cycle of Graham Gibbs consists of six distinct stages to assist in structuring reflective process. They are: Description, Feelings, Evaluation, Analysis, Conclusions, and Action plan ('Reflective practice', 2018, Wikipedia .org)

David Kolb (1984)– Experiential Learning

The learning cycle consists of four stages, they are: Concrete Experience (A new experience is provided), Reflective Observation (any inconsistency between the experience and understanding is examined), Abstract Conceptualisation (Reflection provides new idea or modification takes place in the existing abstract concept), Active Experimentation (applies the learnt concept to the world around) (Kolb & Kolb, 2012)

Reflective Rational Enquiry (2014)

Lawrence Wilkes

An integrated approach views reflection as a cognitive process that bridges the theory practice gap, rooting theory in practice. Critical theory supports rational discursive reflection, validated through equal consensus and socio-political context. It considers

how practitioners can move towards critical reflection within an egalitarian applied learning approach, to challenge a widening theory-practice divide. (Lawrence-Wilkes & Ashmore, 2014)

Linguistic Principles behind the model

There are a few linguistic principles that can be integrated with the reflective strategies to improve the language skills of a learner. The following principles can be incorporated to the metacognition process which can accelerate the acquisition of a person's linguistic ability.

1. Learning from natural contexts

As the child learns his/her mother tongue in natural way, he/she has to learn a second language. The natural learning follows the pattern LSRW, through which the learner becomes more confident using language in variety of contexts. Similar to the pattern of learning mother tongue, the child has to be exposed to the sounds of a language first. In reflective practice strategies also the learner is provided exposure the sounds of the language first.

2. Learning by doing/practice or drill

Any kind of learning a language, practice is the most important aspect in acquiring skills of that particular language. Without practice no learning can be done. This is a process of learning by doing, without doing, no learning is possible. Focusing on all the skills of a language, the learner is supposed to learn by imitating the sounds, reading the text etc..

3. Vocabulary learning

One of the major objectives of learning a language is to acquire mastery over the

vocabulary of the language. Vocabulary is considered as the life blood of a language. Lack of vocabulary is a hindrance which leads to gaps in the communication process.

4. Imitation of sounds and words/oral approach

The learner is supposed to provide maximum exposure to the skills of language by which the learner can be familiar with the sounds of that language. This familiarity leads to the appropriate production of sounds. This is a process that takes place by imitating the first sounds of language.

5. Purposefulness

The teacher has to create a need for communication in the language class, if there is no purpose the learner may not be motivated to communicate in the language. It becomes as basic a requirement in personal as well as in the professional life. A good teacher of English teaches the learner how effectively the language can be used in various situations.

6. Mutuality

For any communication there should be a sender and a receiver, here in language learning, the interaction between the teacher and the taught is essential for exchange of ideas. The mutual bond between the teacher and the learner helps to augment the acquisition of language skills.

7. Selection and gradation

At the outset of the language learning, the teacher has to carefully select and grade them the vocabulary and the structure of the language in order to facilitate the learning. Grade the simple sounds to complex sounding words. If grading does not

take place, the learner may feel some gaps in the process of learning.

8. Correlation with life

Correlation of the subjects with the life of the learner makes the learning, a meaningful activity and a productive one. The duty of the language teacher is to encourage the students to use words and structures of the day to day life. Examples from the life of the learners can be used to promote their curiosity and interest in learning a new language.

9. Maxims of Teaching

Maxims are general truths from real life experiences. The language teacher has to follow maxims like, from known to unknown, simple to complex, concrete to abstract etc.. This is a psychological approach which helps to make language learning as an easier process.

10. Motivation and Interest

The motivation and interest of the teacher towards language he/she teaches, plays a crucial role in developing interest among the learners of English. If the teacher is able to enjoy teaching the language, most probably the learner also will enjoy learning. Motivation can be promoted by providing reinforcements. Interest can be generated by using teaching aids, questioning, sustaining novelty in teaching.

Objectives of the study

The following are the major objectives of the present study.

1. To study the effect of RLAM for acquiring oral communication skills in English.
2. To compare the effect of RLAM for improving the components of oral

communication skills namely, Task completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary and Language control in English

Method of the study

The investigator employed the pretest posttest single group design with a sample of 30 pupils studying in Standard Eight. The experimental group was taught by using RLAM in a language lab setting for one hour for 21 days. At the beginning of the study, the investigator conducted a pretest by giving a topic to speak for two minutes and it was recorded with a recorder to quantify the dependent variable namely task completion, comprehensibility, fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary and language control in English. During the treatment, everyday a topic of their interest was given in the framework of RLAM to the subjects for speaking. A rubric, based on the 6 components of speaking skills for evaluating the components of speaking was applied to evaluate speaking skill. The investigator attempted to compare the pretest and post test scores using t-test. Pretest and post test questions were different but the level of difficulty was same. The study is based on the following three phases.

1. The first phase involved pretesting of the pupils of the experimental group through administration of oral test.
2. The second phase involved the treatment, which consisted of instruction based on the RLAM over a period of three weeks to the experimental group.
3. In the third phase, a posttest on oral communication skills was administered to the pupils to test the effect of RLAM on oral communication skills.

The syntax of RLAM

Phase I -Experiencing content – The instructor provides clear instructions about how to communicate on a particular topic, and gives a model talk(exposure to the language)

PhaseII-Imitating for acquisition – Here learner starts speaking on the topic, the instructor jots down the corrections required.

Phase III -Reflecting the learning group

process – Every student is given chance to analyse the wrong expressions/usages made by himself and others.

Phase IV -Analysing the thinking strategy – Everyone has to write down on what they have learnt that day newly.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1

The pretest - post test scores of the components of Speaking by using RLAM in the treatment

Components of Speaking	Tests	N	Mean score	Standard Deviation	t- test for Equality of Means		
					t	df	Sig.
Task Completion	Pre	30	1.31	0.65	4.50	29	.000
	Post	30	1.84	0.53			
Comprehensibility	Pre	30	1.34	0.62	3.464	29	.002
	Post	30	1.79	0.59			
Fluency	Pre	30	1.1	0.53	2.773	29	.011
	Post	30	1.5	0.59			
Pronunciation	Pre	30	1.36	0.38	1.904	29	.071
	Post	30	1.57	0.52			
Vocabulary	Pre	30	1.16	0.42	3.215	29	.004
	Post	30	1.50	0.58			
Language Control	Pre	30	1.20	0.53	1.501	29	.148
	Post	30	1.36	0.64			
Speaking Overall	Pre	30	7.47	3.13	4.43	29	.002
	Post	30	9.56	3.45			

Data and Results of Test of Significance of the Difference in the Pretest Post-test scores of Speaking of RLAM in Experimental group

From the table it is clear that the means of the pretest scores of the students in the experimental group is higher

than the means of the posttest scores of Experimental group for the components of Speaking Skills in English namely Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and overall scores on Speaking Skills in English.

The obtained t values for speaking skills are Task Completion ($t_{(29)} = 4.50, p < .05$), Comprehensibility ($t_{(29)} = 3.464, p < 0.05$), Fluency ($t_{(29)} = 2.773, p < .05$), Vocabulary ($t_{(29)} = 3.215, p < .05$), and the overall scores on Speaking Skills in English ($t_{(29)} = 4.43, p < .05$) are significant at 0.05 level. Whereas Pronunciation ($t_{(29)} = 1.904, p > .05$), Language Control ($t_{(29)} = 1.50, p > .05$) are no significant at 0.05 level.

It is obvious that there is a significant difference between the means of the pretest scores of the components of Speaking Skills namely, Task Completion, Comprehensibility, Fluency, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Language Control and overall scores on Speaking Skills in English. The result of the study agrees with the findings of Netto(2008) who found that the intervention of Reflective thinking strategy of teaching is more effective than conventional method of direct instruction for the achievement in chemistry, for improving metacognitive awareness and in the achievement of affective variables among secondary school students.

Major Findings of the Study

There is significant difference in pretest and post test scores in task completion component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students. Therefore, RLAM is effective in developing the skill of elaborating content appropriately in English corresponding to the theme given.

There is significant difference in pretest and post test scores in comprehensibility component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students.

Therefore, RLAM is effective in developing the skill of expressing content comprehensively in English requiring no interpretation on the part of the listener.

There is significant difference in pretest and post test scores in fluency component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students. Therefore, RLAM is effective in developing the skill of expressing a content continuously in English speech with few pauses or stumbling.

There is significant difference in pretest and post test scores in vocabulary component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students. Therefore, RLAM is effective in developing the skill of expressing words continuously in English with adequate and accurate use of vocabulary.

There is no significant difference in pretest and post test scores in pronunciation component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students. The reason might be that the time for the experiment conducted was not sufficient enough to develop pronunciation of a foreign language with an entirely different pattern of the production of sounds.

There is no significant difference in pretest and post test scores in language control component of oral communication skills among the secondary school students. The reason might be that the time for the experiment conducted was not sufficient enough to develop control of basic language structures of a foreign language of different basic structures.

Conclusion

The instructional design RLAM is a simple solution for teaching new or foreign languages to a group of students having only the very basic fundamental skills of language, provided that, the teacher should have the mastery over the language as well as the knowledge of the linguistic principles of learning a language. All teachers who teach English should have basic proficiency in English (National Curriculum Framework, 2005). If the teacher is capable of using this effectively, miracles can happen in the speedy acquisition of the language. It is suggested that the teachers teaching L2, can fruitfully utilize the strategies of reflective practices for teaching second or a foreign language.

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